

MORFOMETRIK PARAMETERS OF THE STOMACH OF EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES STUDYING THE ROLE OF BRAIN TRAUMA

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Actuality. The world on the frequency of brain injury 2% per year has been increased by more severe types of the brain have been detected since the number of types has increased to make more. Among traumatic injuries traumatic brain injury (BMJ) is a critical problem in neurosurgery incredibly modern. The structure of the trauma letallik total of 30-50% to BMJ comes on. In heavy type letality to 85% is. Thus, changes in the whole body and central gumoral reflektor will appear. The amount of blood a lot katexolaminlar separated in the case of the sympathetic nervous system reaction is the priority. This initial days as a result of reactions in the central disorders of the whole body appear mikrosirkulyasion minutes. Will bring this system disorders of the body affected, including in the gastrointestinal tract.

The purpose of the research. Comparative study of gastric parameters in different periods of mild brain trauma and morfometrik in the norms, the development of the method of correction.

Materials and methods. Bukhara state medical institute 2020-2022 200 years of experimental research in the laboratory rats obtained from mature sex white and healthy. All of the observed control and 3 experimental animals were divided into groups in accordance with the research objectives. The results of research on the subject as mild experimental brain injury incurred after 1-,3-,7-,14-,21-,28- the breed of white rats in the day without kardial the stomach, and the body pilorik histological biomaterias be extracted from the experimental test results conducted to assess the condition of the central nervous system of animal psixonevrologik served. For experimental research, morfometrik, immunogistochemical, psixonevrological, as well as statistical research methods have been applied.

The results of the study. We will breed a healthy and microscopic examination of the stomach rats white mature sex the total thickness of its wall, mucosal, submucosal, muscular layer thickness, the height of the folds of the stomach and we can measure the depth. Check this option active parts namely the body and the stomach sekretor pilorik part in the country was conducted.

Sex mature and gland cells of the stomach pilorik the hardware part will breed healthy white rats Syan (tsitoplazma core ratio) when the number 3 in the learn from the intersection point of the average net core okulyar 5tagacha $3,9 \pm 0,27$ than average number of from 9 to 20 units tsitoplazma far $13,8 \pm 1.1$ than it was. Syan this case 2,8 3,6 from 5 pm average $\pm$ is equal to 0.2. Hanging on a beam walk tests and morris water mazes like PN psixonevrologik brain injuries in experimental animals before and after was done. Using this test, which is characteristic mainly for acute bmej of action, balance, memory, learning functions, such as the breakdown of the cns were assessed in a comparative manner.

Psixonevrological signs for hanging on a beam walk test effective brain injuries and informative. This test task from the application of acute traumatic brain injury of the central nervous system of action, and function is the evaluation of the effects of calamities koordinasiya statika. White mature and a healthy sex without seed placed in the special kallamushlar width 2 cm, length is 150 cm from a wooden beam was held. Using light white rats the dark side. A wooden beam hanging on white moving in kallamush videotasvir will breed to get, and pass the time from slip and fall due to review its beam will determine the number of beams.

White mature and healthy seeds hanging wooden beam test pass kallamushlar sex withoutida, the following results were obtained. The reconstruction of the transition time from a wooden beam hanging-from 3.8 4,7 pm, an average of 4.2 ± 0.1 seconds. From a wooden beam at the time of passing than 3 times the average slip due to the number 5 far $3,9 \pm 0,3$ than it was. At the time of passing from a wooden beam due to the fall, while the number of 2 martatagacha average of 1.2 ± 0.2 to set up.

Conclusion. The effects of mild brain injury secondary changes of parameters in gastric morfometrik considering the results of a pathological condition I was trying to explain the mechanisms of genesis. This research, which is observed in mild brain injury and workers of the central nervous system and in violation of the correction in the treatment of organic functional changes it gives character to choose.

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